

PySCF-MRCC INTERFACE: PLATINUM STANDARD ELECTRONIC STRUCTURE CALCULATIONS WITH ARBITRARY INTEGRALS

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By making it possible to run the MRCC software directly in Python from PySCF, we open the door for nearly any scientist to easily run some of the most accurate electronic structure calculations possible (for example, CCSDTQP).

Previously, MRCC had interfaces with the CFOUR, COLUMBUS, DIRAC, MOLPRO, ORCA, and PSI4 computer programs, but all of these programs do not officially support the calculation of integrals involving Gaussian basis sets with $L=7$ or higher, and MRCC on its own cannot do integrals with $L=9$ nor any integrals for Hamiltonians associated with relativity (for example the X2C Hamiltonian). PySCF can easily do integrals with $L=9$ and with the X2C Hamiltonian, and despite being by far the youngest software mentioned here, it has more contributors on GitHub than any of the other programs mentioned. PySCF is not only an open source software, but also an “open development” software, which combined with being written in Python, has contributed to its unusually rapid growth for a quantum chemistry software: this makes us confident that for any “arbitrary” Hamiltonian, if there is a reason to use the Hamiltonian and a practical way to calculate the integrals, PySCF will be able to calculate them via its engines for calculating integrals (libcint and qcint) comparatively soon after enough interest in such calculations arises. Our interface allows MRCC to do electronic structure calculations with these “arbitrary” integrals provided by PySCF. The interface can also be modified to glue some other electronic structure packages with MRCC, for example OpenMolcas (which can also easily do integrals with $L=9$) or any software that can print its integrals in the FCIDUMP format.